

Study On Elite Configuration In Obi Regency Extension Of North Maluku

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Abstract: The research was aimed to find the configuration of an elite in an extension of Obi Islands Regency of South Halmahera - North Maluku; to map on contrastive elites of extension and interest, and of pro-group conflict of Obi Islands Regency extension. The method used in this research is a case study method by qualitative approach. The research method is the purpose to describe, record, analyze and interpret conditions occurred in the field. The research result shows that extension of Obi Islands Regency is boosted by geographical aspect. The extension plan of Obi Islands Regency causes pro and contra between inside and outside elite of Obi Islands. The contrastive elite extension is the Regent of South Halmahera (Muhammad Kasuba). It is caused that the Regent has the economic interest (business entity) in Obi Islands. The interest competition happens to the pro-group extension of the elite in Obi Islands against the elite in Ternate City. The rivalry among pro-group of extension, basically, is competition to get an influence and support from Obi's society and effort to maintain and/or take resource away in Obi Islands after the extension become the rivalry factor of pro-extension elite. The conspiracy happens because of the economic interest in pro-extension elite (Abu Karim La Tara, and Hi, Subur) against with contra-extension elite (Muhammad Kasuba as the Regent). This conspiracy is in terms of defending and securing business entity (economic interest) in Obi Islands' territory. Whereas, the elite configuration happened, in fact, is the collaboration with/between ethnicity and religion aspect. Therefore, the geographical aspect occurred is polarity among Obi elites. Polarized Obi's elites based on region either Obi Islands' territory, Labuha-Bacan and Ternate as well have mounted interest rivalry among the individual elite of Obi existed in North Maluku Province.

Index Terms: Conspiracy, economic interest, elite competition

1 INTRODUCTION

The presence of regional autonomy provides flexibility for regions to regulate and manage their own areas in accordance with local conditions and take into account potential of the area. Law Number 32 the Year 2004 regarding Local Government, which is a substitute for Law Number 22 the Year 1999 as a formal legal from an implementation of regional autonomy, brings new paradigm in an implementation of local government. As a result of local government flexibility in carrying out its authority has many implications in the field. One of the most prominent and continuing implications to date is the desire for various provinces, regency/city to split their territories into new autonomous regions. Based on Law Number 32 the Year 2004, the formation of regions is basically intended to improve public services in order to accelerate the realization of community welfare as well as a means of political education at the local level.

Meanwhile, according to Government Regulation No. 129/2000 on Requirements for Establishment and Criteria for Extension, Elimination, and Regional Merger, the explanation states that the purpose of regional extension is always directed to improve community welfare through 1) improvement of public services; 2) accelerating the growth of people's lives; 3) acceleration of regional economic development; 4) acceleration of regional potential management; 5) improvement of security and order; and 6) enhancing the harmonious relationship between center and regions. To that end, the formation of regions must consider various factors such as economic capacity, regional potential, area, population, and consideration of social, political, socio-cultural, defense and security aspects as well as other considerations and conditions that enable the region to organize and realize the purpose of region establishment and the granting of regional autonomy. The development of the regional extension in present time, not in accordance with reality. Many problems arise as a result of the policy, which tends to divert the purpose of making regional extension policy. The birth to regional extension euphoria is also quite alarming, as many of regional extension proposed are based solely on the less substantial issues. This can be seen from the number of new autonomous regions causing problems, for example, horizontal conflicts arise out of local communities and vertical conflicts between the regions and parent regions, the infrastructure is not yet available, the bureaucracy and office facilities as a place of government is not yet available and most importantly to finance the governance process still depends on parent or central government. In other words, the extension of existing areas tends to be a burden on central government. If this issue is properly scrutinized, many new regional divisions are realized due to the political interests of a handful of people without regard to region dimensions, which are either political dimensions, administrative/technical dimensions and intergovernmental dimensions of inequality. Several studies on the regional extension have been conducted by various researchers. Study on dynamics of elite response Papuan People's Assembly (MRP) in West Papua Province formation. The results showed that there was a different response from MRP elite, which was between support

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and Contra to West Papua Province formation. For those who support the establishment of West Papua Province, they are an MRP elite group originating from the regional part of West Papua. As for MRP elite originating from the regional part of East Papua (Central Province) and region of Central Papua tend to be counted. However, this does not mean that none of these groups are liberally or antagonistically in response to West Papua Province formation. The election of MRP elite into three regions, it also tends to show the fragmented elite based on ethnicity [1]. In addition, the elite argumentation encourages distribution or accumulation that seems to be different form and opposite, in fact, it is all driven by the same reason that is the actualization of elite power. Elites who already have power and legitimacy seek to reveal their roles, duties, interests, and influence in local governance. The work of reasoning with the actualization of elite power in distribution and accumulation arena is marked by their involvement in policy formulation process and opinion formation [2]. Meanwhile, political and democratic conditions in North Maluku Province, especially since reform era, are strongly affected by political parties, public participation, and local political elites [3-5]. Based on the above studies, it has been shown what happened to region extension so far. This study highlighting on an elite configuration in an extension of Obi Islands region in South Halmahera Regency. So, the expected result can know how elite configuration is done in Obi Island Regency extension, either from an aspect of ethnicity, geopolitical aspect, and religious aspect. In addition, there is no study of elite configuration in a regional extension of Obi Island, or at least there is a difference between/in research methodology and mind frame used. Based on the above description, it is interesting to study related elite conflicts in regional extension, interest motive in a handful of an elite in the region and resources distribution always appeared along with region division. This phenomenon often occurs information of new autonomous regions.

Defenition and Elite Type

The word elite was used in the seventeenth century to describe perfectly quality goods with special virtues, which were then expanded to refer superior social groups, such as first-class military units or high rank of nobility [6]. In other definition, elite is the position of the community at the top of most important social structures, namely, high positions in the economy, government, military, political, religious, teaching and free jobs [7]. The term elite also refers to a minority of persons appointed to serve a collectivity in a socially valuable way. The elite is effective and responsible minorities-effectively looking to the execution of interests and concerns to others where the elite is responding. The socially meaningful elite is ultimately responsible for the realization of ultimate social goals and for the continuation of social order [8]. Simply stated, elite is defined as most talented members of society such as educational, religious, and organizational elite. However, in sociology perspective, elite is more directed to political elite [2]. The assumption of an elite theory that divides elite and common people is an inevitable trait in modern, complex societies wherever [9]. The elite is a small group that derives most of its value, the elite refers to those who are influential. Moreover, concerning the ruling elite expressed by Harold Laswell is "a class consisting of those who succeeded in occupying dominant positions in society, in the sense that the values they form (create, produce) are highly valued in a

society that concerned". These values may be tangible power, wealth, honor, knowledge, and others. They succeed in acquiring and mastering such values of large numbers, in turn occupying the upper layers of the stratification that exists in the society concerned. Conversely, those who are lacking or even unsuccessful at all acquire and master those values will be at the lower layers of stratification. Elites are individuals that succeed in having most part of values that exist because of their personality traits and qualities [10]. Based on nature and character of the elite, individuals belonging to elite can be divided into 3 (three) types, namely elite that is oriented towards personal interests or class, liberal elite, and elite Contra-type [10]. An elite group of a personal or group-oriented type can be declared as having a tendency to be closed, in sense of rejecting other non-elite groups to enter the group. Those who are members of elite try to collaborate to keep the situation going. Therefore, this type of elite can be declared to have a conservative nature, in which attitude and behavior tend to maintain qua status. Elites of this type can also be said to be less responsive to aspirations and demands that develop in society; what is important to him is the fulfillment of interests of his class. Liberal-type elites have attitudes and behaviors that lead to the creation of a conducive atmosphere that provides the widest opportunity for every member of society to change its social status. Elites of this type provide the same opportunity for non-elite members of society to compete with a healthy way to become elites. The existence of equal opportunities and fair competition for members of society to enter elite environment make the movement of community social status relatively easy to change. Liberal-type elites have high responsiveness to aspirations and demands of society. Contra elite groups are oriented towards audiences by opposing any form into the establishment or by opposing any form of change. By opposing establishment or change, those who are members of contra elite group have extreme, intolerant, anti-intellectualism, certain racial superiority characteristics, and use violence in their aspirations. This group can be separated from the left wing, which always demands radical and revolutionary changes and right wings that are always opposed to social, cultural, economic or political changes. Nevertheless, this group, either left wing or right wing, shows itself as a group that brings people's aspirations.

Definition of Elite Configuration

The term configuration is interpreted as an arrangement, structure, composition, form; entity (to describe people or objects) that is sequentially and interconnected with each other. The idea of configuration has the same meaning as in astronomy: the position of planetary corpses in relation to each other. In the elite study, the configuration means relative position and size of various elites (politics, bureaucracy, capitalist, managerial, cultural, religious, and military) in the constellation of power. The elite configuration reflects structure, social, economic, cultural, and political relationships that exist within the community itself. The elite configuration marks a significant difference [11]. Minority control over majority is done in an organized manner, which places majority standing just behind, let alone minority usually consisting of superior individuals. If Pareto mentions a political class that contains diverse social groups [12]. The emergence of an elite configuration in society is more result of limited power relations. It is said to be limited because it involves only

those parties that have dominant power only in dynamics of local political-economic activities. In turn, the whole process has led elite conscious or not, to better focus their thoughts and actions on their own interests. Thus, the elite does not have enough care to fight for public interest in general and more concerned with his personal interests in order to get the resource. The political process of any level in its estuary is the formation of an elite configuration. Here, there is an exchange of interests in elite groups that determine the political pendulum. However, in the local context, the implications may be in an impasse of democracy. At very least, the elites tend to only strengthen the ranks. With the aim of reaping political-economic benefits of a limited political clan. The risk, the public is not experiencing touches that are more advanced, perspective and revolutionary within a framework of local policy and policy choices. The situation will be worse when rulers generated from a political process will regard themselves as 'tops' of socio-political strata that all words must follow and be approved for all their actions. The local elite's configuration is controlled by the spirit of self-interest, group, and family. Thus, it is not surprising when a family network of a public official will assume existing position belongs to his family. It is not surprising that people enter family network near a regional head feels like an official as well. Based on the explanation of this description, we can understand that elite configuration are basically position and composition of various elites in terms of politics, economy, bureaucracy, religion, social, and others. Differences in elite position of resources have the configuration so that the elite's resources have different interests. The interests in elite always coincide with resources, but with limited resources, elite will be in touch with other elites in influence to make sure that what they choose is best to be implemented for common good in the name of public interest.

Elite Configuration Patterns

Whereas in any society, the newly emerging society that has been able to build a more established civilization, which developed into a powerful society, in it, there are two classes of society that is class controls and who is controlled. The first class, always in lesser numbers, exercises all political functions, monopolizes power and benefits from power it exercises. Meanwhile, the second class, much larger, directly controlled and controlled by first class [13]. In every society, the difference between its members is affected, only variety and degree of difference that distinguishes one society from another. In a relatively homogeneous society, the differences between members of a society can be expressed as relatively inconsequential and neither diverse. This is because in a relatively homogeneous society usually has a population that is not so much, and variety of life that is cultivated by members of the community is also not so varied, and these conditions will, in turn, lead to a less complex relationship between community members. This rather inconspicuous and less diverse distinction can be found in *gemeinschaft* society as described by Ferdinand Tonnies, or in the society described by Emile Durkheim as being attached to mechanical solidarity. A person or group of people have certain advantages, and then with these advantages able to play a prominent role and have influence over branch of economic life can be declared as elite in the economic field; while a person or group of people that have advantage and then concerned can play a prominent role and have a great influence over politics field

can be declared as an elite in politics field; and so on in other areas of life. However, it is possible that a person or a group of people with the advantages possessed capable of playing a prominent and influential role in more than one branch of life may be concerned in addition to being an economic elite is also an elite in politics field. The elite is those who earn the most from what is earned, and the three most valuable things to gain are honor, income, and security. A single elite can monopolize or buy up either three rewards or some elite coexisting with them. The base of elite power is basic capital and superiority that makes elite have power, including elite positions, such as economic, political, social, cultural, religious, military, skill and other competencies, and power or influence capable of creating adherence to people or groups others in society, including the object of obedience.

The Governing Elite and the Non-Governing Elite

In connection with the assumption that in every society must require the presence of leaders, then individuals or groups of individuals that have certain advantages, in general, will emerge as a leader in the community. With their own inherent advantages, they will direct other individuals in social life. In connection with this, Pareto or Mosca expressed his opinion that in every society, whether a society that is still traditional or modern, must be found a small group (minority) of individuals that rule other community members. It is further stated that a small group of such individuals or elites in the community may be termed governing elite and non-governing elite. It is explained that those belonging to ruling elite consist of individuals occupying political positions, and those belonging to non-governing groups consist of individuals that are not occupying political posts but have the capacity to influence directly making of wisdom. The ruling elite can be regarded as political elite. Political elites are those who have the political office in the political system. Political office is the highest status that every citizen obtains. In any political system, any political structure or power structure is always occupied by an elite called political elite or ruling elite. The most superior elite is the group of political power; because in politics field its decisions are accompanied by most powerful sanctions, political power is seen as a value that has the power of 'glue' that can lead to other values 'follow it'. The political elite encompasses all holders of power in a political building. This elite is made up of those who succeed in achieving dominant positions in the political system and people's lives [14]. While the non-governing elite is individuals or a group of elites that have no power to governor not to occupy political posts but have the ability to directly influence decision making/policies exercised by ruling elite, this elite comprises of; economic elite, cultural elite, religious elite, educational elite, and so on.

Elite Patterns Working Together

The elite group in principle consists of various statuses; politics, bureaucracy, economy, social, religion, and others. Differences in elite status do not make gaps between each elite, but the similarity with goals to achieve something expected to create good cooperation among the elite. The elite relationships of various social statuses in cooperation are always intertwined with one another in order to achieve the goal. Relationships between elites can occur horizontally and vertically. Horizontal relationships occur when elites have equal social status; economic elites with other economic elites, political elites with political elites, bureaucratic elites with

bureaucratic elites, religious elites with religious elites, and so on, who share the same goals and interests among elites. So that each elite has relationships with each other to work together to achieve their interests. Meanwhile, the vertical relation is a relation that is established between the elite equal to the higher elite social status/ruler and has the same goals and interests. For example, the government and/or smooth its personal interests in the business, then the effort must be done by the economic elite is to cooperate with the political elite higher / have the power so that the desired plan of the economic elite can be realized as expected and vice versa. Political elites have an interest in obtaining higher resources but lacking the capital to achieve the desired political objectives, thus having to cooperate with the economic elite; borrow capital as a form of cooperation between the two elites. Internally, the elite is homogeneous, unit, and has group consciousness. The elite is not a collection of mutually exclusive individuals, or simply sum of people alone. But on the contrary, the individuals within elite know each other well, have similar backgrounds and have same values, loyalty, and interests. For this, there is a saying that elite group has "Three K", namely awareness, wholeness, and unanimity of group goals [14]. The individuals belonging to an elite group are relatively integrated, homogeneous and closely related to each other. Those who occupy top positions in economic, military and political fields come from relatively similar social and life backgrounds. Their views of life show many similarities because most of them have the same educational background, have the same religion, so they often meet in clubs organized by the same social groups. The elite consists of a system of interdependent parts, each participating in institutionalization and here it enters the old term with a new meaning. By institutionalization, we will easily understand all classes and leaders who play an active role in community organizations. They may be self-appointed entrepreneurs, or selected judges and others [8]. The interdependent nature of each other inherent in economic, military or political elite can be expressed as certain factors result in social structure. An important social structure is the form and degree of economic decentralization, military, and political institutions that are so great. With the form of large institutional arrangement implies that elites in decision-making process must consider each other's interests. A high degree of centralization implies that decisions and actions of elites in each institution will result in extensive relationships, both within the institution itself and in the wider community. With other statements can be stated that elites of three institutions are doing actions that are complementary in making and implementing decisions process that apply and binding all members of the community. In addition to social structural factors that cause cooperation among elites, the social psychological factors also contribute to the occurrence of these links. Social psychological factors arise from the background of elite and social experience is relatively same. Those who act as elites come from similar social background and worldviews. They have same educational, geographical, ethnic and religious backgrounds, and they often associate themselves with same social groups. Thus, the factor of social psychology, then elite of various social status can unite and cooperate between elite with each other.

The Cross Elite Pattern

The character or attributes attached to an elite in a society is

not necessarily same as character or nature of elites in other societies. It is at least determined by the type of society in which elite resides, and is also determined by its cultural nature. The existing environmental conditions within a society and different ideologies that elites may influence the elite's view of cooperative relations. Attitudes and actions of an elite in an effort to achieve its goals and interests can affect cooperative relationship among the elite. Thus, the similarity between goals among elites does not necessarily establish good cooperation, but the differences in interests in each elite competition so that among elite opposite. There is the possibility of a shift between elites. Elites that have certain values are likely to be shifted positions of influence by elites that have other values. To maintain its position as an elite group that has influence in process of making and implementing decisions that bind the community, the elite is required to have certain skills. The skills that elites need to possess can be tangible skills ranging from the ability to convince and manipulate. All of which is to maintain its position as a superior group compared to other groups. So, elites that do not have certain skills not being able to convince public and its position can be shifted by other elites that have skills and other values, so elites that do not possess these skills and values are opposed to other elites. The social structural factors and social psychology do not dictate long-standing cooperation between elites. However, the competition of interest in obtaining the resources can make a difference in the elites so that each elite prefers opposites to other elites that have different and competing interests in competing for the same resource. Distinguish interests in the elite to gain influence, support from society and resources; political, social, and economic is something that often happens among the elite. Each elite has its own resources and seeks to use it for its political interests. There are several factors related to differences in influence, among others. The differences in political resources distribution, the diversity of which people use their political resources, the vast diversity of resources which people use for their political purposes [15]. Thus, the elite is not always a pattern of cooperation; the elite is a relatively integrated group, homogeneous and closely related to each other, the existence of social structural factors and social psychology so that among elite interconnected. However, the elite also sometimes patterned each other across the elite with each other. The main factor of the elite pattern are opposite each other, it is because different goals and competing interests to get the resources are limited.

2 RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The research was conducted in two areas of South Halmahera Regency. The first area in the capital district of Bacan, and the second area in Obi Island. The Obi Island is an area separated from the parent regency, so the territory divides itself into a new regency, as seen in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Location of Research

This study uses case study methods that research conducted intensively, thoroughly, and deeply against a particular organization, institution, or symptoms. The case of this research is regional extension: Pro-Contra and Conspiracy. Therefore, we are trying to develop concepts and collect data that occur in the field, study intensively cases that have occurred and dig as much opinion on parties that are considered competent with study problem. The approach is done through qualitative methods. This research method aims to describe, record, analyze and interpret conditions that occur in the field. With this method it is expected that we can know deeply, to express problem by describing clearly and factually in accordance with data obtained in the field, so that we can know elite configuration which is done in extension of Obi Island Regency either from geographical, ethnicity, and religious aspect, pro-contra motive of regional extension, competition of interests of pro-local extension group, and conspiracy motives among elite. Data collection of this study used primary data source and secondary data source. The primary data source is the source of data obtained directly from the respondent, while the secondary data source is the source of data obtained through documents, archives, and others at agency related to the research. The primary data source of this research is secretary of South Halmahera Parliamentary council, politicians, bureaucrats, public figure, people of religion, and other people that are competent. To obtain the required data, the data collection techniques used are; a) observation, ie observation and recording of systematic to symptoms that occur in the field. We directly involved in activities of respondents, so the data obtained according to research problems; b) interview, which is question and answer between we and respondent, interviews are intended to obtain detailed data on respondents; c) documentation is data collection by recording or quoting from documents or archives (regulation, newspaper, magazine, internet) required to complete primary data obtained directly from the respondents. The data analysis in this study is to pay attention to steps taken in a qualitative research. The steps are; a) data

collection; b) data assessment; c) data interpretation; d) data analysis; e) data deduction. From these steps, the data that have been collected from various sources need to be prepared first before further processing, it aims to obtain comprehensive data in accordance with objectives of the study. To obtain data validity, then in this analysis will use data triangulation technique, which means cross and check between data sources with one another, and between resource persons with each other. So drawn the conclusion of a significant analysis of studied problems.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The people vote for supports extension is a key condition for sustainability of extension process. In the current constellation of legislation, the people role has not been explicitly stated so that in public administration practice votes is represented only by local elites in the region. The extension context of Obi Islands region, the idea of the regional extension comes from Obi Island elite. The elite is Abu Karim La Tara as Camat Obi, to succeed extension idea, thus forming the Obi Caring Forum (FPO) which was attended by all Village Heads and Village Consultative Board (BPD) to state the attitude and support extension. Not only Obi Island elites, the elites in Labuha-Bacan region of South Halmahera Regency capital also established Obi Family Association (IKO) and expressed its support for Obi Island extension. In addition to elites in Obi and Labuha-Bacan Islands, elites in Ternate region also formed the Extension Committee of Obi Island Regency as part of a manifestation of extension. The elite configuration in the extension of Obi Island Regency turned out to be a mix of ethnicity and religious aspects, while geographical aspects of differences and disharmony occur among Obi elites. Differences and disharmony among elites based on their respective interests, resulting in competition and different interests of extension pro-elites, on the one hand, to defend resources owned by the elite and on another side of interest to get power distribution of power after extension.

Geographical Aspects

Indonesia is a continental country consisting of various large and small islands. In the Constitution of the Republic of Indonesia, Article 18A states that regional divisions of Indonesia over large and small areas, with the form of government arrangement established by law, by looking at and remembering the basis of deliberations in state governance system, and rights of origin in special areas. Logical consequences of the island nation, many regions demand and want to an extension in order to improve people welfare in the region. Geography becomes jurisdiction boundary of the territory occupied by a people group that become formation condition of an autonomous region. The geographical situation, strongly influenced, seen in various aspects and is universal, so used as an autonomous region. The concept of giving authority on region due to the presence of a number of inhabitants an area, where the group has differences and interests. Differences in geography in addition to formation basis of a common identity of a group also differences formation in characteristics of territory, problems, and authority of each autonomous region. Based on geography, the region has local characteristics, conditions and interests and problems formed by its different geographical characteristics. The division of regions is separation part of several regions into their own autonomous regions. Separation of escape

sense from parent regions and/or form new areas within the province. The region extension is inseparable from various existence dimensions triggering emergence of demands for extension of new autonomous regions, the dimension can be seen from (1) political dimension; geography factors, socio-cultural factors, demographic factors, and historical factors, (2) administrative/ technical dimensions and (3) dimensions of inequality between regions. Geopolitical conditions and regional strategy of Obi Island, the basic reason for the formation of regions. In addition, from the side of the span of control is very far from the central government of South Halmahera Parent regency. The geographical factor of autonomous regions is aspect related to the formation of autonomous regions as a result of political emergence motivated ties between people living in a region. These bonds can be grounded by geographic and historical entities so that people feel connected by a political bond. Strong weak bonds are highly dependent on how much political appeal to the presence of society as a political unity [16]. Geographical factors, ie factors that assume geographic conditions of a region will affect identity formation of a community group that will eventually develop into a single political entity. Communities that are geographically separated to tend to form a separate community and will form the basis of community group formation. In the context of Obi Island region, the polarization of the Obi people, especially the elites based on geography, makes competition and differences of interest among elites. Identity as a son of Obi Islands region and one region does not necessarily strengthen the bond between each elite. However, geographic or territorial differences in activities as bureaucracy, politicians, and academics have led to competition and different interests of the elite in fighting for Obi Islands Region extension.

Ethnicity Aspects

Indonesian society consists of various ethnic groups and races (multi-ethnic), this condition then is categorized again in groups based on social, economic, political, and religious status. Such differences are indeed the wealth of a society. With these differences, there arise bonds between ethnic groups of each other. The bond between kinship or primordial (blood and family) and similarity of tribe, language, and custom are factors of close bonding in society. Ethnicity becomes the main factor in fighting for the extension of the region, not accommodating of certain ethnic interest in government level cause distrust of ruling ethnic. So, ethnicity is often used as a power base to get support from ethnic communities. Ethnicity persists because it relates to need for the identity of a person or group society. While there are great similarities with other ethnicities, it does not prevent them from feeling different. A strengthened ethnic identity, where ethnic identity is increasingly highlighted in social life as it has recently happened to other areas. Ethnic used as a political tool to gain a higher bargaining position in obtaining certain resources. However, differences in ethnicity within a region can also form a solid community bond. The formation of community bonds with some ethnic groups due to the similarity in the territory within an archipelago. Feelings of fate and arms with doing activities (farming, fishing) as an archipelago society would make this as a force built on the local wisdom of society itself. So when felt not pay attention to service affairs undertaken by local government, distribution of development, it caused public unrest to make movement demanded region

extension. The social movement built by people to demand regional division is not only done by one dominant ethnic but a combination of several ethnicities in the region. The ethnic blend is intended, to give confidence to the government that in fact, people in a unit region want region extension. Although there are hidden political interests carried out by certain ethnic groups. Obi islands territory majority of its population come from 2 (two) ethnic of Buton and Tobelo. However, ethnic groups of Obi islands have no ethnic origin and ethnic Obi are referred to as ethnic immigrants. All ethnic groups of Obi Islands region come from various regions, ethnic Butonese originating from Southeast Sulawesi, Tobelo ethnic from Halmahera archipelago, Kei ethnic from Dual-Maluku, Buginese ethnic from Makassar-South Sulawesi, Sanana ethnic from Sula Islands, Tidore ethnic from Tidore City, and Makian ethnic from the Makian-Halmahera Islands, which later settled in Obi Islands. When regional extension, then identity is often highlighted as a basis for gathering support from the community. Ethnic part of identity that is always built between the community with local elite, which ethnic is most dominant in a region in demanding the division of ethnic concerned will be more accentuated that extension due to elite services derived from the majority ethnic.

Religion Aspects

The religious equality embraced by society in a region is a strong factor of forming a bond based on religious teachings. The condition of religion in the region is the very determining pattern of daily life in society, especially in performing worship activities. Religion is sometimes an important identity trait for an ethnic group, but sometimes it does not mean anything and only as a belief of a particular ethnic member. Obi Islands region is a region that deeply upholds religious values that have been ingrained, they have been socialized with religious diversity of North Maluku formation. The spread of religion in Obi Islands is inseparable from the existence of 4 (four) kingdoms in North Maluku the four sultanates referred to be Sultanate of Ternate, Tidore, Jailolo, and Bacan. As a whole can be distinguished from three areas of religion spread, namely; 1) the territory of Ternate Sultanate includes Ternate Islands, North Halmahera, and Sula Islands; 2) the territory of Tidore Sultanate covers the Tidore Islands, Central Halmahera and East Halmahera; and 3) the territory of Bacan Sultanate includes Bacan and Obi Island. The division of Obi Islands Regency is part of the struggle for entire community and Obi elites to be achieved become new autonomous regions. The aspect of religion in regions division into political power of society and elites to fight for an extension. Because all Obi elites together to unite determination to fight for and split Obi Islands into regency without discriminating against the favor of religious side. Although the religion in Obi Islands is predominantly Muslim (67.3%) and Christian (32.4%) and the rest is from Confucianism (0.3%), Obi elites remain unit to voice the demands of Obi Islands Regency extension. Among the adherents of both Obi society and elite, is bound in a bond between tolerance and large families between tribes and islands. Attachment to some ethnic because based on past history (Moloku Kie Raha). The historical factor, which is the main pillar of religion spread in Obi Islands region. So religion with one another has a bond that cannot be separated from ethnicity. The majority religion (Islam) in Obi Islands is of Buton ethnic origin, while Christianity comes from Tobelo ethnic. Despite this, ethnic Tobelo is also largely converted to

Islam.

4 CONCLUSIONS

Geographically Obi is an archipelago located in southern part of South Halmahera Regency. With archipelago condition, Obi Island consists of Obi Major and Minor. As an archipelago consisting of various ethnicities and religions as well as acculturation and primordial relations of Obi community, the span of control away from the center of government is a major factor in demand for the regional extension. In the context of Obi Island regency extension, the geographical aspect tends to evoke the spirit of Obi community from various regions in North Maluku Province to demand region extension. While ethnicity aspects and economy are not at all highlighted in the discourse of extension, because socio-economic, socio-cultural life of Obi people already tied in a bond of tolerance and family among ethnic groups, as well as in livelihood most people come from farmers and fishermen. The extension of Obi Islands Region has caused pro and contra among elites in South Halmahera Regency. The pro-extension comes from Obi community and Obi elites, while contra-extension is an elite that comes from outside Obi island. The opposite elite, the Regent of South Halmahera Muhammad Kasuba, the Contrapart has an economic interest (business) in Obi Islands region and owns 20% stake in 3 (three) companies operating on Obi Island. Economic interests, the main reason for not wanting to release Obi into a new regency. Despite pro and contra of extension, it turns out there is also a conspiracy of some elite in affairs of economic interests (business ventures). The elite conspiracy occurred between pro-extension elite (Abu Karim La Tara/ Obi Subdistrict and Hi. Subur/Entrepreneur) with elite contra-extension (Regent Muhammad Kasuba). Equal economic interests; personal gain, securing and sustaining a business venture are main reasons for a conspiracy between elites. The pro-extension elite in smoothing everything connected with its business must cooperate with the contra-extension party as Regent of South Halmahera, and vice versa. Elite contra-extension must cooperate with Obi elite to get support for his business to run smoothly without any obstacles. The configuration of the elite in Obi Island extension, there was a mixture of ethnicity and religion, while from the geographical aspect there was polarity among elites. The polarization of Obi elite based on the good territory of Obi Islands region, the Labuha-Bacan region (South Halmahera Regency), and Ternate, has created a competition of interest. This competition in elite groups of extension in terms of interests in each elite to seize influence and support from communities, to secure and retain resources owned and interests to obtain power distribution of post-extension.

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